

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A SELF-LEARNING MODULE IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN 9

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to develop and evaluate a self-learning module for *Araling Panlipunan 9* to address persistent challenges in teaching Economics and improve the low National Achievement Test (NAT) scores in this subject. Employing descriptive research methods, the study utilizes examinations and surveys alongside Johnson's Instructional Materials Development Approach as its primary framework. Participants included Grade 10 students from Manaring Integrated School and expert Social Studies teachers from the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. The findings indicate that: (1) the designed and validated self-learning module effectively enhances students' learning experiences in *Araling Panlipunan 9*; (2) the modules are well-designed, aligned with curriculum objectives, and suitable for the student's educational needs; (3) the modules are validated as reliable and appropriate for the learners' assessed levels, needs, and abilities; (4) students can use the modules easily due to their comprehensible design; and (5) incorporating the self-learning module is an effective method to supplement traditional teaching approaches in *Araling Panlipunan*. Therefore, the developed self-learning module is recommended for classroom use in teaching Economics and as a model for creating comprehensive modules for the remaining quarters of the school year.

Keywords: *Araling Panlipunan 9, Economics, Johnson's Instructional Materials Development Approach, National Achievement Test (NAT), Self-Learning Module*

INTRODUCTION

The “No Filipino Child Left Behind Act of 2008” is directed to safeguard and secure the right of every citizen, especially children, to quality education. The said policy also ensures to advance access to such education. In support of the aforementioned, the state shall craft appropriate frameworks and resources for an effective implementation of educational programs, projects, and services; and encourage local initiative for the enhancement of schools and community-based facilities for learning. The policy mandates that children of compulsory school age would be required to attend school and enjoy the benefit of having the opportunity to be educated. It also ensures that schools and other facilities reflect the values of a community by permitting teachers, learning facilitators, and other personnel to be flexible in satisfying the needs of the learners, as well (Cayanan, 2015).

To determine if the schools are effectively implementing the “No Child Left Behind” policy along with other programs geared towards quality education, annual assessment strategies have been implemented to assess the current learning situations across the country – one is a national standardized examination. The National Achievement Test (NAT) is designed to determine each learner’s academic levels, strengths, and weaknesses in five curricular subject areas at the end of the school year; this is in accordance with the Department of Education Order No. 5 s. 2005 on Students’ Assessments at the National and Division Levels of Basic Education.

The Department of Education (DepEd) reported an average of 47.6 percent in the year 2011 and 54.22 percent in the year 2012 in *Araling Panlipunan*. In Region 02, *Araling Panlipunan* secured an average of 59.6 percent for the School Year 2014-2015 in the National Achievement Test. Based on the results of the 2011 and 2012 NAT; there was an increase of six percent in the learners’ mastery level of key concepts and competencies in *Araling Panlipunan* (Social Studies). The increased percentage shows that there is an improvement in the learners’ knowledge of *Araling Panlipunan*. However, there is still a high discrepancy between the reported NAT results and the government’s target criterion level of 75 percent, as directed by the Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (Macarandan, 2014). Hence, the low performance of learners in *Araling Panlipunan* in the National Achievement Test indicates the need to augment the learners’ mastery level of concepts and competencies in the said subject through improved teaching and enhanced curriculum material development.

Aside from the low average performance in the NAT in *Araling Panlipunan*, there are still common and basic problematic situations cited for the low performance in the subject. One common problem teachers encounter inside the classroom is that students tend to have a low attention span during discussions.

According to Balena (2004), social studies could be uninteresting for students, especially when the teacher does not relate topics and concepts to the trends relevant to the subject. Thus, it could be inferred that integrating current trends in discussing social studies will avoid an academic monotone atmosphere in a classroom setting in the

integrative teaching of Social Studies. Other problems teachers face are a lack of textbooks, deficiency of physical facilities conditions, and lone teaching of knowledge-skill-values. In this situation, there is a need to frame and develop textbooks and other materials relevant to the demands of teaching the subject.

On the other hand, teachers are also encountering time constraints in teaching social studies. Teachers are having problems incorporating broad concepts in Social Studies because the Department of Education reduced the number of meetings to 110 days only (Macarandan, 2014). Furthermore, the emergence of trends in teaching Social Studies that have been discussed presents additional concerns. There are negative relationships between the Social Studies area and students' attitudes, experiences, and perspectives. Admittedly, the negative relationship may be caused by different degrees of difficulties in materials, teacher-student relationships, classroom environments, lack of interest, and not recognizing social studies as a way of learning from the past the things that can be applied in the future.

Social Studies is an important academic component of high school but it is usually taken for granted (Sievers, 2005). Further, Social Studies subjects are not encountered with the most positive experiences by the students in school when compared to other subjects such as English, Mathematics, and Science. To address these concerns involving the instruction of Social Studies or *Araling Panlipunan* in the Basic Education Curriculum, there is a need to further innovate for solutions in the instruction process because Social Studies is very essential in the holistic development of learners (Edar, 2012; Bechayda, 2007).

Fundamentally, the Social Studies program is based on information, skills, and value perceptions. Therefore, the concepts, skills, and values should be understood and acquired using different strategies of instruction. Delivery modes could be class lectures, note-taking, homework assignments, tests, and quizzes. Class activities may also include role-playing, cooperative groups, discussion, film/video presentation, and experiential activities. With this, numerous methods and approaches could be implemented to augment and aid the teaching of Social Studies. Hence, there is a need to develop instructional materials (Ramos, 2004; Agorilla, 2014).

The *Araling Panlipunan* Curriculum under the K to 12 Basic Education Program recognizes the importance of modular instruction in the teaching-learning process in the 21st century and as supplementary materials to cope with extending time to cover the lessons in schools with more than one session (Macarandan, 2014). Research results confirm the effectiveness of modular instruction and reliability in identifying difficulties and concerns in carrying out the new curriculum. The modules motivated the students to participate actively in the learning process because the activities were interesting and moderately difficult (Macarandan, 2009). One thing more, the use of a modular approach as an innovative way of instruction design provides students with an opportunity to achieve meaningful learning (Edar, 2012). It tends to make the teaching-learning environment more active and attractive to learners in terms of information gathering, independent learning, and problem-solving.

Learning modules meet the educational principle of individualized instruction. Modular learning allows students to progress at their own pace and abilities. Notably, to provide quality education, one should recognize the essential role of instructional materials in purposeful and effective instruction (Naval, 2014).

An educational authority stated that the development of the production of textbooks and other instructional materials based on the student's interests, knowledge, understanding, abilities, needs, and experiences is necessary to achieve the objectives of education. Instructional materials have been effective instruments for providing quality education by meeting the needs of students.

To meet the needs of students, the learner-centered curriculum gives priority to developing self-directing and independent lifelong learners who can apply in real life their understanding of the concepts (Cayanan, 2015) as specified in the desired outcomes of the K to 12 Curriculum competencies in the form of content and performance standards in each learning area.

Economics is an integral component of the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum under the *Araling Panlipunan* Curriculum which is a subject undertaken by Grade 9 students and is focused on the Philippine Economy. It aims to make students deeply understand the economic stability of the nation, and eventually, learners would be able to transfer these concepts to real life by practicing creativity, demonstrating critical thinking, problem-solving, and wise decision-making.

Generally, learning economics has its incentives (Zaide, 2009). First, it tells us about the material influences in daily life as a family, in the community, and as a nation. Second, knowing economics makes a person better at keeping and making money. Third, through economics, an individual learns about how to be a good businessman and perhaps a good public official someday. Fourth, economics teaches about the issues of agriculture and commerce that affect the lives of individuals and the country in general. Lastly, the knowledge of economics is necessary to be able to manage problems brought by modernization and it also helps people to prepare for their future.

The unpredicted occurrence of COVID-19 (Corona Virus Disease-2019) pandemic put the world into a major health disaster. The safety and protection of the people, including school children, are at risk. To protect everybody, schools, teachers, and students are not allowed to go to school for normal activities- classes, programs, and others to avoid contact that may transfer the deadly virus from one person to another. The government has planned and implemented national strategies to cope with the global pandemic.

In the education sector, the Department of Education of the Philippines through its Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) amidst the pandemic strategized and innovated solutions so that schools would not close and education would go on at all levels. Among the coping strategies arrived at and decided upon are the blended learning approach, distance learning, modular learning approach, virtual learning approaches through online platforms, and other means and resources.

Before the pandemic, it can be said that developing and using modules in the classroom was for intervention and enrichment purposes. Teachers prepare modules to help a student cope and master the least mastered competencies and lessons. Now, with the advent of COVID-19, the use of modules is an official alternative mode of learning under the blended approach. The learning material should be prepared and produced by observing the design prescribed by the DepEd. In the local context, teachers should prepare the modules according to local needs. Thus, module development is a required task for a teacher who desires his students to learn meaningfully, effectively, and productively.

As a response to the need to augment the learning experiences of learners amid a global pandemic, the researcher is encouraged to plan and design an example of a learning continuity modality learning materials such as learning modules to address the learning needs of the students as prescribed on the Learning Continuity Plan of the DepEd.

The researcher believes this study will contribute to the field of *Araling Panlipunan* specifically in providing supplemental activities and learning experiences aside from the central and general provision of learning modules by the Department. The series of learning modules developed are contextualized for real-life applications. The modules are not foreign but supplement the most essential learning competencies that DepEd provides upon the implementation of such learning delivery modes.

Relative to the perennially pressing need for relevant instructional materials to effect quality instruction, and meet the “No Contact Policy”, and the call for “Bayanihan, Heal as One”- a battle cry for unity and cooperation among Filipinos to fight against the ills brought about by COVID 19 pandemic, the present study is an immediate and practical response of the researcher.

Conceptual Framework

Teachers and experts in education are continuously looking for strategies in teaching and learning that can better help students learn more effectively and productively.

Today, the models of the Whole Child Approach, 21st Century Skills, and Project Based Learning are believed to be among the most effective approaches to assist teachers and students achieve the objectives of education. Likewise, the Modular approach promoting independent learning is also proven to be another effective strategy.

Social Studies is a subject area designed to build productive, civic-minded, critical, and informed individuals. The subject consists of diverse areas such as economics, geography, history, civics, government, culture, law, and religion from Kindergarten to Grade 12 up to tertiary level. Grade levels of students determine the curriculum content systematically arranged from simple to complex. The competency components of the Social Studies curriculum include cognitive thinking processes, analytic skills, continuance of participation, and principles/concepts for students and use as an

application of life within today's society. Social Studies is expected to teach the students (Thiveos & Moroz, 2011 cited in Macarandan, 2014) life and career skills, learning and innovation skills, information, media, and technology for them to succeed in the 21st century (P12 Century Skills).

Economics is a field in the social sciences. It is under the curriculum of *Araling Panlipunan*. The phased implementation of the *Araling Panlipunan* Curriculum for Grades 7-9 in School Year 2014-2015 raised concerns among teachers. With the new set of competencies, gaps in learning standards came up. An example of the issues is the incoming Grade 9 students who can no longer take the subject World History but will immediately take Economics, among others. The issue was addressed by the issuance of DepEd Order No. 20, s. 2014 stipulating policy guidelines on the implementation of grades 7 to 10 of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and clarifying courses of study in *Araling Panlipunan*. Economics, now with improved and more comprehensive learning competencies, remained to be taught in *Araling Panlipunan*. This eventuality raised new concerns regarding books, textbooks, and other materials to use in teaching Economics effectively. Unfortunately, it was found out by educators that most books were somewhat erroneously written, and reconstructing the books would take an author time to finish. However, educators and teachers are given leeway to develop and produce materials that follow the learning competency guidelines and standards.

The books or materials are under prescribed learning competencies dealing with economic problems and issues in the Philippines, advantages and disadvantages of policies adopted as well as the status of current and alternative economic order from the Philippine Journal of Development in 2007. It is predominantly important to know that economic understanding implored at least a basic understanding of operation (Zevin, 2000) because the economic system is an essential part of everyone's education from birth to death. The economic forces that control the structure of society influence our very existence, hence, it is imperative to make Economics an integral part of the entire social science curriculum. Accordingly, it is imperative for teachers with specialization in a chosen area in Social Studies should be equipped with capabilities to organize, design, and develop curriculum materials appropriate to the individual levels of students (Salandanan, 2009).

Vitasa (2006) Modular instruction is beneficial for several reasons: first, the modules help the individual needs in learning different skills and concepts; second, compared to using textbooks, they are more effective and economical in developing knowledge and skill; third, they introduce learning with minimum teacher direction and supervision; fourth, they ensure satisfactory minimum standards; fifth, modules upgrade the content and enhance competencies in grammar; sixth, they integrate theory and practice and provide resources for distance learning; and seventh, they encourage mastery of learning and lastly, they encouraged a changed role of teachers who become facilitators of learning.

The researcher, a teacher of *Araling Panlipunan*, is beset with the need to develop instructional materials in *Araling Panlipunan* to meet the needs for remedial and

enrichment activities to further help the students optimally acquire basic skills in Economics. Indeed, the researcher is inspired to develop teaching modules to produce the desired learning outcome for the educational success of the students. To carry on the project, the researcher anchored her study on Johnson's Model of 1972.

According to De Guia (2016), Johnson's Model characterizes instructional materials from planning to disseminating and evaluating, hence, a very good approach toward developing learning modules in Araling Panlipunan specifically in Economics. This provided the methods of research and procedures for developing and innovating instructional materials appropriate to the design of the researcher's proposed modules. Johnson's (1972) Instructional Materials Development Approach is composed of a design phase, development phase, and dissemination phase.

In the first phase of Johnson's Model, a survey of existing materials accumulated through the years affirms the claim that the design and use of instructional materials that no new materials are completely new. A survey of existing materials enabled material developers to identify aspects of design and use them to serve as a prototype or model. Then, the survey also leads to a definition and justification of the rationale for designing new material. The writing of the table of specifications comes next. These specifications detail the instructional materials developed, the format, and the technical materials that had been identified.

The Development Phase is primarily selecting appropriate materials. The next step is writing of learning materials according to the table of specifications. The developed learning materials were validated and assessed by the experts. In this study, the validation and assessment were performed by her research adviser and teachers of Araling Panlipunan.

Further, formative evaluation is followed by conducting a judgmental review or pilot testing in the form of a controlled tryout of the instructional modules. The formative evaluation for suitability was conducted utilizing judgmental review with representative teachers responding as evaluators or judges. An evaluation tool was adopted from the Department of Education and likewise elicited feedback in the form of comments. Based on the information gathered from the evaluation and try-out, writers can make necessary revisions to the materials before final production. The final production of the materials should be carried out as instructed in the objectives of the materials, the detailed writing specification, and the proposed format.

Lastly, the Dissemination Phase deals with the acceptance and adoption for use of the new instructional materials. This stage refers to the extensive use of the new instructional materials in the final format. In this stage, the instructional material developer and designer should work closely with the students, teachers, and administrators for further feedback on the effectiveness and functionality of the materials.

The functionality of the instructional materials and teaching guides means that teachers could study and use the guides with ease during their classroom instruction because each teaching guide contained pertinent information and featured strategies

that would tickle the playful and imaginative minds and feelings of students (Cayanan, 2015) to achieve the desired objectives.

Developing a material would facilitate a realistic and concrete view of teaching-learning and help the students gain a better understanding of the concepts being taught (Salandanan, 2009; Macarandan, 2014). Therefore, the use of learning modules in teaching *Araling Panlipunan 9* can be an effective strategy for developing a functional learner equipped with the understanding of concepts and principles linked with real-life situations.

Figure 1. Johnson’s Model of Instructional Materials Development

The figure above details Johnson’s Model for Instructional Materials Development as one of the main frameworks for the study. This cites the three discussed phases of the model – the design phase, the development phase, and the dissemination phase. The design phase includes activities such as proposing a new set of materials, preparing the table of specifications, and initial writing of the materials. In the development phase, initial evaluation and improvement of the materials are done, while the last phase shows the process of modification, final revision, and extensive use of the materials. Thus, a systematic process and system of preparing and developing materials in a subject area.

The researcher, therefore, developed teaching modules based on Johnson's Model as the main blueprint and framework to produce the desired learning outcome for the educational success of the students. The modules provide the students a unique avenue in the writing process based on the premise of writing in the discipline of Center for Educational Measurement no. 30 s. 2006.

Figure 2. Research Paradigm on the Development and Validation of Learning Materials in Teaching Araling Panlipunan 9

The figure above shows the graphic presentation of the research procedure indicating specific steps undertaken for the first, second, and third phases. As gleaned from the figure, the design establishes the rationale for the study, research focus, and review of pertinent literature following the review of the conceptual framework.

Research Objectives

This study purported to develop and validate a self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan 9 aligned with the structure of the Enhanced Basic Education K to 12 Curriculum and contribute to the improvement of student performance in the teaching-learning process.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Design a learning module in Araling Panlipunan 9 to be utilized by students in the Grade 10 level.
2. Establish the content validity and reliability of the learning module in terms of face, content, organization, and effectiveness; and
3. Test the effectiveness of the learning modules in teaching Araling Panlipunan 9.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive method of research. The descriptive type of research is integrative for qualitative and quantitative methods of collecting data. Descriptive surveys as research methods include questionnaires and normative surveys (Gray, 2004). The descriptive type of research was appropriate for gathering information about existing conditions that determine and report the way things are (Emotin, 2003).

Sampling and Participants

The study involved two sections (Aquamarine and Zircon) in the Grade 10 level of Manaring Integrated School. The utilization of the self-learning module was conducted before the implementation of the new curriculum in Araling Panlipunan wherein Grade 10 students take Economics subject which the researcher has been teaching for five years.

In the use of the descriptive method, the self-learning module was subjected to validation using the Expert's Assessment Checklist which was developed based on several theses by Hernandez (1999), Libranda (2004), Salvador (2005), Rivera (2011) and Agorilla (2015). The researcher adopted the criteria set by the writers, which were found to be appropriate. The checklist was used to validate the learning modules based on format and design, content, organization, and presentation. Two (2) teachers of the Schools City Division of Ilagan, and one (1) teacher of the Division of Santiago City were the validators of the learning modules. Of the three, two were Teacher III and one Master Teacher I. Eighteen (18) Araling Panlipunan teachers teaching Araling Panlipunan 9 from the Division of the City of Ilagan and forty-five (45) students from Manaring Integrated School also evaluated the learning module.

The sampling method used was cluster sampling which involves surveying whole clusters of the population selected through a defined random sampling strategy (O'Leary, 2004 cited in Agorilla, 2015). Clusters may include schools, geographic locations, or sections. The clusters are sampled so that individuals within the group can be surveyed or interviewed. It was used as reasonable but relatively diversified groupings which was evident in a statistical population. In this technique, the total population was divided into two groups, and a simple random sampling of the groups was done. Using the lottery technique, the researcher selected a class from the two sections in the Grade 10 level. The selected classes used the module/instructional materials. The students of the second section (Zircon) were considered for the first pilot testing of the learning modules while the students of the first section were considered for the second pilot testing.

The study was conducted in Manaring Integrated School, a public institution under the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan located specifically at Manaring, City of Ilagan, Isabela. The students came from different barangays of the city including Pasa,

Manaring, Bangag, Capo, Tangcul, San Isidro, San Juan, Rugao, San Andres, San Rodrigo, and Balla.

Instruments

In the gathering and collection of data, the researcher used the following: (1) Experts' Evaluation Checklist of the self-learning Module to gather and collect data on the validation and evaluation of the learning modules in terms of objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectiveness; (2) Pretest and Posttest for each self-learning module to achieve the scores to test the effectiveness of the learning modules; and (3) Students' Evaluation Checklist of the self-learning Module to collect data on students' evaluation on the self-learning module in terms of content and format.

1. Experts' Evaluation Checklist of the Instructional Module

To have a basis for determining the acceptability of the developed instructional modules, the researcher used the Expert's Assessment Checklist which was developed based on Agorilla (2015). Since the Self-Learning Module in Araling Panlipunan 9 was constructed and developed by the researchers, this was validated by the experts using a standardized assessment checklist. Some modifications to the item format were made to better align them with the purpose of the study. Revisions were validated by the researcher and teacher experts in module writing in Araling Panlipunan.

2. Pretest and Posttest Scores

Pretest and Posttest were used as instruments to achieve the scores that are necessary to test the effectiveness of the self-learning module. In developing the achievement test, the researcher adhered to the standard procedures in developing and validating a test: (a) development of the table of specifications; (b) construction of the test items in congruency with the objectives and content; and (c) testing the validity and reliability of the test.

3. Students' Evaluation Checklist of the Instructional Modules

This instrument is a five-point Likert checklist adapted from the theses of Marasigan (2003) and Torre Franca (2017). Unlike the expert's evaluation form, the checklist for students focused only on the content and format of the developed instructional modules yielding a total of 20 items. The self-learning module content evaluation was composed of the objectives, lessons, scope, competencies, and other essential and relevant elements in the self-learning module. Finally, the evaluation of the self-learning module format centered on the layout of the module, template, font, size, symbols, diagrams, and other relevant technical aspects of the self-learning module.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection activities that were undertaken in the study are described as follows:

Material Development and Validation Stages

I. Design Phase

The researcher examined books and related materials in the self-learning module of Araling Panlipunan 9 which are the topics under the fourth quarter. It was suggested by the research panel that the last quarter of the school year was the most efficient for the researcher and the students to conduct and implement the utilization of the self-learning module. The researcher also referred to and checked the desired learning competencies, scope, and sequence prescribed by the DepEd for Grade 10 high school students. The goal of the researcher at this stage was to create a matrix that would show the competencies that must be demonstrated in the self-learning module. Deciding and determining the competencies to be captured in the learning module were accomplished in the second phase.

The content of the self-learning module was guided by the course description by the DepEd and the prescribed topics under Social Studies. Araling Panlipunan 9 introduces learners to the world of Economics. In this subject, learners are expected to demonstrate the result provided as the basis for determining the coverage of the self-learning module. A table of specifications was prepared to serve as a guide in the preparation of the learning module. The specification includes the module number, the title, and the skills developed in each learning module.

Module No. and Title (Modyul)	Skills/ <u>Competencies</u> (Kasanayan)
Module 1. <u>Konsepto at Palatandaan ng Pambansang Kaunlaran</u>	<u>Matutunan ang tungkol sa konsepto at palatandaan ng pambansang kaunlaran upang maka bahagi sa pagpapabuti ng pamumuhay at masukat ang kaunlaran ng isang bansa.</u>
Module 2. <u>Sektor ng Agrikultura</u>	<u>Matutunan nag kahalagahan ng agrikultura sa pang araw-araw na pamumuhay ng bawat Pilipino upang makibahagi sa matalinong paggamit ng mga likas na yaman at pagsunod sa mga patakarang pang-ekonomiya.</u>
Module 3. <u>Sektor ng Industriya</u>	<u>Matutunan ang papel na ginagampanan ng industriya at ang ugnayan nito sa maayos na pamumuhay ng mga mamamayan upang masiguro ang kapakinabangan sa pagtamo ng kaunlaran.</u>
Module 4. <u>Sektor ng Paglilingkod</u>	<u>Matutunan ang bahaging ginagampanan ng sektor ng industriya sa bansa upang mapabuti ang kakayahan ng mga manggagawang Pilipino at tumaas ang produktibidad.</u>
Module 5. <u>Impormal na Sektor</u>	<u>Matutunan ang kontribusyon ng impormal na sektor sa ekonomiya ng bansa upang mapagtagumpayan ang kahirapan sa buhay.</u>
Module 6. <u>Kalakalang Panlabas</u>	<u>Matutunan ang bahaging ginagampanan ng kalakalang panlabas sa ekonomiya ng ating bansa upang mabigyang linay ang nagaganap sa pagitan ng Pilipinas at ibang mga bansa sa daigdig.</u>

Figure 3. Talaan ng Inskripsyon

The table of specifications of the self-learning module was considered in the selection of appropriate instructional events. The different learning activities for each self-learning module were identified as well as the role of the teacher and the learner.

To ensure the success of each instructional event, the conditions of learning must be relevant to the expected outcome; hence, the methods of instruction were selected to help the learners achieve the skills.

Identifying Teaching-Learning Strategies, Educational research has proven that teaching strategies that are interactive, multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, integrated, experiential, varied, and connected to students' daily lives are effective (Rivera, 2012 and Agorilla, 2015) also added that varied and appropriate instructional materials are needed to make instruction more motivating and encouraging.

II. Development Phase

Writing the Self-Learning Module is the major part of the development and validation of the module in Economics. Its writing was anchored on the K to 12 curriculum which was signed into law as Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum on May 15, 2013. The criteria set by the Department of Education Material Council and the UNESCO guidelines in developing instructional materials in terms of the objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectivity in writing of the learning module were carefully considered. Suggestions from the panel members and the advisers during the proposal defense were incorporated into the development of the learning material.

The style adopted for the self-learning module was patterned from the existing English Learning Modules by Soriano (2013) in her thesis “Development and Validation of Self- Self-Instructional Modules in Grammar for Grade 5 Pupils” due to similarities in objectives and purposes.

Writing the first draft of the self-learning module was done using the following components:

- A. Overview (Lagom Pananaw). This part of the module outlines what students are about to learn. It gives pieces of information on the different concepts that they encountered throughout the learning tasks.
- B. Target (Sapulin). This refers to the objectives that students are expected to know, do, or feel after accomplishing the module.
- C. Break In (Tanong Ko, Sagot Mo). This refers to the section that carefully cues the learner on the skills and values to be learned through process questions.
- D. Discover (Matuto Ka). This refers to the facts about the lesson to be presented through sentences or picture analysis.
- E. Try This (Kaya Mo Ba ‘To?). This part of the module includes series of initial activities which measure learners’ comprehension and understanding of the lessons and concepts presented.
- F. Challenge (Henyo Ka Ba?). It allows the students to do more of the activity to achieve a desired understanding of the concept or skills.
- G. Move On (Sagot Pa More). This part of the module is another series of activities that serve as an application of the concepts and lessons for retention.
- H. Things to Remember (Pakatandaan). These refer to the concepts that the students need to remember after covering certain parts of the module.
- I. Post-Test (Panghuling Gawain). This element is a short summative assessment that will measure the students learning based on their scores. Each module consists of 10-item multiple-choice test questions based on the objectives and content of the lesson discussed.
- J. References (Sanggunian). The sources of information and relevant data necessary for the series of activities and the discussion.

The objectives for each lesson were taken from the Learning Competencies for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. In this stage, the researcher decided to adopt objectives based on the topics included in each module. There were 6 lessons covered by the Self Learning Module. In determining and preparing the instructional activities for each lesson, and in preparing the pre-test and post-test the researcher ensured that the texts were written in clear and appropriate language suitable to the level of the target Grade high school students. The language used in the module is Filipino. This is based on the mandate that Araling Panlipunan or Social Studies in Basic Education must be taught in the Filipino language.

III. Dissemination Phase

This stage highlights the preparation of a self-learning module in terms of face, organization, and content validity. This was undertaken to bring out the prepared self-learning module in terms of face, content validity, and reliability.

Validation by Experts

Content validity is the degree to which a test measures topics and areas that it is intended to measure (Sevilla, 1998). The appropriateness of the learning material to the subjects and congruence to the objectives are determined through the help of the experts.

The self-learning module underwent validation using the Expert's Assessment Checklist. The criteria focused on the clarity, attainability, and measurability of the objectives, specifically in terms of knowledge, processes, understanding, and performance. These criteria align with the focal points of assessment procedures in the K to 12 Curriculum.

For the organization, the criteria include clarity and conciseness of instruction; proper sequencing of the lessons, progression, and depth of knowledge, provisions of adequate questions, and problems, and relevance of the learning module to the objectives. The criteria for the learning module include varied and diverse resources to widen sources for knowledge and to augment learning and students' prior knowledge and skills in using the material.

The effectiveness of the self-learning module focuses on its usefulness in guiding the student, promotion of active learning and practicality of application, and motivation for learning.

The experts used the revised "Experts' Assessment Checklist" (Agorilla, 2015) which is specifically crafted for material evaluation. Experts' ratings were subjected to SPSS Version 19.0 Cronbach Coefficient Alpha and Inter-rater reliability to determine the internal consistency reliability of their responses.

Establishing the Validity of the Self-Learning Module

The development and validation of the self-learning module was anchored on the K to 12 Curriculum in Araling Panlipunan which intends to produce learners who are competent, productive, resourceful, and research-oriented and where teachers are expected to facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner.

The criteria for establishing the validity of the self-learning module face, organization, reliability, validity, and effectiveness were set by the Department of Educational Material Council.

Assessment by Experts

Three experts were chosen and were asked to rate the individual components of each criterion using a rating scale. The three experts were selected based on their capability as instructional material developers.

One of the experts is a Master Teacher I of the South District, of the City of Ilagan who has been teaching Araling Panlipunan for several years and at the same time a coach of Araling Panlipunan-related academic and non-academic contests at the regional and national levels. He is also noted for delivering his expertise in producing his functional and comprehensive modules that enhance students' knowledge and skill in all aspects of Araling Panlipunan particularly in Economics subject. He is also one of the demonstrators on Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in the Division of the City of Ilagan, Isabela who motivates teachers to find ways and means to lessen drop-out and failing students in all subject areas.

The second expert is an instructional material developer. She is a faculty member of San Antonio District of the City of Ilagan. She developed lessons using modules to cope with the challenges identified in teaching the subject area.

Finally, the third expert is also an instructional material developer. He had already devised and utilized instructional materials such as modules in teaching Araling Panlipunan which are anchored from the principles of localization and contextualization. He taught for several years and served as the Araling Panlipunan Coordinator and the Supreme Student Government Adviser at the same school. He excels in the field of Social Science.

Validation by the Teachers and Experts

Standard Deviation was used to gauge the evaluation of the experts and teachers on the objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectiveness of the self-learning module as well as the general evaluation of the students on the format and content of the self-learning module. The calculated means were qualitatively described using the following guidelines:

<i>Mean Range</i>	<i>Description (Experts/Teachers)</i>	<i>Description (Students)</i>
1.00-1.49	Needs Improvement	Strongly Disagree
1.50-2.49	Not Satisfactory	Disagree
2.50-3.49	Satisfactory	Moderately Agree
3.50-4.49	Highly Satisfactory	Agree
4.50-5.00	Outstanding	Strongly Agree

The mean rating for each criterion was computed by getting the average of the mean rating of the experts. The grand mean for each criterion were again computed to obtain the mean for each criterion.

For instance, materials were provided to augment the instructional events and skills to be acquired by the learners. It shows that experts fully conceded that the competencies cited in the assessment tool were congruent with the competencies set by the K to 12 Curriculum in Social Studies.

Proofreading, Editing, and Printing of the Self Learning-Module

The instructional materials were subjected to grammar and spelling checks on the computer while encoding. After auto-editing on the computer, the text, graphics, formatting, and layout were carried out for the artistic appearance to make it more student-friendly. The arrangement of various features, elements, and components was checked by the experts to ensure that the learning module is clear, consistent, and correct.

Evaluation of the Materials by the Adviser and Distribution of Evaluation Forms to the Teacher Expert

The developed self-learning module was presented to the thesis adviser for comments and suggestions before the evaluation of experts. Teachers and experts who were subjected to evaluate and validate the learning modules developed in AP for the students were also given evaluation forms and the materials to be evaluated.

Initial Revision of the Self-Learning Module

Comments and suggestions initially given by the adviser were taken and duly noted to revise and modify the learning modules developed for the students in *Araling Panlipunan 9*.

Second Revision of the Self-Learning Module

The self-learning module in *Araling Panlipunan 9* was revised based on the experts' suggestions and recommendations. Revisions were made to follow the suggestions of the Experts regarding the format of the tasks in the learning module. However, only a few parts were taken down for revision due to the compliments and positive feedback given by the teachers and experts to the modules developed.

Third Revision of the Self-Learning Module

The self-learning module was revised after the pilot testing. The revised module was tested to gather the rating of the performance task outputs from the teachers and individual students were analyzed statistically to determine the inter-rater readability of each performance task output.

Utilization of the Self-Learning Module

The revised self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan was administered to forty-five (45) Grade 10 Aquamarine students of Manaring Integrated School from January 15, 2015 to March 10, 2015. The individual scores of the students from the pretest and posttest from each learning module were subjected to paired sample t-tests to determine the effectiveness of the modules. The ideal p-value obtained from the test should be less than 0.05 to be considered significant and the p-value should be less than 0.01 to be considered highly significant (Valdez, 2014). The last step in the validation of the Learning Module in Araling Panlipunan 9 was problems encountered in the second pilot test and recommendations from the experts, peers, and students were then utilized for further refinement and revision of the materials.

The revised self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan was administered to forty-five (45) Grade 10 Aquamarine students of Manaring Integrated School from January 15, 2015 to March 10, 2015.

In evaluating the developed self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan 9, two sources of information were used by the researcher: (1) feedback from the student-respondents on the content and format of the instructional modules they used; and (2) results of the comparison of the student-respondents' performance in the pretest administered before the modules were given to them and the posttest conducted after they were done with the modules. Eventually, the instructional modules were finalized based on the inputs from the evaluation stage.

Data Analysis

1. The perception of the students and teacher-evaluators was determined on the effectiveness of the material (in terms of format design, objectives, content, organization, presentation, and usefulness), therefore, frequency and weighted mean statistical tools were used.
2. The Cronbach-Alpha Coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency reliability of the responses from the teachers and experts.
3. The scores taken from the pretest and posttest were treated. To determine if there is significance in the test levels of the students, the T-test for dependent samples was utilized.
4. A Paired Sample t-test was done to compare the ratings indicated by experts and students on the format and content of the modules.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that before, during, and after the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the school where she is employed, and other concerned offices to conduct the study.

2. The researcher wrote a letter to the respondents and conducted a short orientation on the nature of the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality.
3. The researcher through a letter of consent sought approval of parents to allow their children to participate in the study.
4. The researcher strictly observed proper citation for authors, books, e-sources or any publications using the 7th Edition of the American Psychological Association (APA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development of Self-Learning Module in Araling Panlipunan 9

The self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan 9 was developed by the researcher through the help of her research adviser, suggestions of the experts, and the use of learning materials for K to 12 learners and other resources. After it was developed, the module was used by the Grade 10 students.

The following figures show some parts of the completed self-learning module.

<u>Pamantayang Pangnilalaman</u>	<u>Pamantayang Pangganap</u>
<p>Naipakikita ng mga mag-aaral ang pag-unawa na ang globalisasyon ay may kaugnayan sa pagpapabuti ng kalagayan ng iba't ibang sektor ng ekonomiya. mga patakarang pang ekonomiya nito sa harap ng mga hamon at puwersa tungo sa pambansang pag-unlad.</p> <p>Napahahalagahan din ang paglahok sa kalakalang panlabas ay mayroong mga patakaran at programang pang-ekonomiya na ipinatutupad ng bansa.</p>	<p>Ang mga mag-aaral ay aktibong nakikibahagi sa pagsasanay ng isang pagpapasiya tungkol sa globalisasyon sa pamamagitan ng pakikipag-ugnayan sa impormasyon, pagpapabuti ng sector ng ekonomiya at mga patakarang pang ekonomiya gayundin ang epekto nito tungo sa pambansang pag-unlad.</p> <p>Nakapagsusuri ng mga artikulo na nagpapaliwanag sa paglahok ng bansa sa panlabas na kalakalan na isa sa mga patakaran ay ang programang pang-ekonomiya.</p>

Figure 4. Pamantayan sa Pagkatuto

Pamantayan sa Pagkatuto (Learning Objectives). The first part of the self-learning module gives a view of the general learning expectations to be developed amongst the learners. These learning expectations include the content objectives on activities and skills to be executed by the learners. These are strategically derived and based it on the three important aspects of learning development—cognitive, affective, and psychomotor learning domains.

Figure 5. Grapikong Paglalarawan

Grapikong Pantulong sa Paksa (Learning Graphic Guide). This part introduces the graphical presentation of the main point of discussion. This outlines the general and specific topics to be discussed briefly and comprehensively in the succeeding parts.

Sa bahaging ito ay lilinangin ang mga kaalaman tungkol sa pambansang kaunlaransa tulong ng mga impormasyon at mga inihandang gawain bilang batayan sa pagkatuto. Halina't simulan.

Aralin 1	PALATANDAAN NG PAMBANSANG KAUNLARAN
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Naniniwala ang pamunuan ng City of Ilagan na ang pag-unlad ay bunga ng isang progresibo at aktibong proseso. Halimbawa nito ay ang makabagong pamamaraan ng pagtatanim ng mais na kinapapalooban ng isang proseso, at ito ang pag-unlad. Ang bunga nito ay mas maraming ani, at ito ang pagsulong hango sa aklat ni Feliciano R. Fajardo na Economic Development (1994).

Figure 6. Matuto Ka (Aralin 1)

Matututo Ka (Discover). This refers to the facts about the lesson to be presented through sentences or picture analysis. This part of the module enhances learners' understanding of the concepts specifically of national development.

Sagutin ang mga sumusunod na gawain bilang pagsasanay sa pagkatuto.

Panuto: Pansinin. Suriing mabuti ang kalagayan ng bawat larawan na nasa ibaba. Isulat kung Gusto o Ayaw ang nais mong larawan sa ating bansa at ipaliwanag ang iyong napiling kasagutan.

1. _____
2. _____

Figure 7. Unang Pagsasanay

Kaya Mo Ba To? (Can You Do This?). This refers to the exercises to be done. From the discussion and highlights of the main concepts, learners shall further do an activity that will challenge their understanding through a series of questions and photos of inquiry

The overview of the self-learning module shows a framework for what students learned and the information on the different concepts they encountered throughout the learning tasks. The learning objectives were also written to provide outcome statements that target the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the students and be able to exhibit and develop after the lesson. Each lesson starts with a pretest to determine the students' prior knowledge regarding the topics, which the teacher would aid in teaching the lesson.

Various activities highlighting the concepts in Economics were added to check students' understanding and to assess to which extent they could apply the things that they have learned. To have actual scores measured, a posttest was given at the end of the module. This determines the student's level of achievement from the targeted learning objectives. Lastly, references were included in the module to cite contributory materials and other sources relevant to the learning activities and concepts in Araling Panlipunan 9.

Reliability of Expert and Teacher ratings

Table 1. Internal Consistency of Expert and Teacher

Material	Cronbach Alpha
Module 1	.93
Module 2	.92
Module 3	.92
Module 4	.95
Module 5	.93
Module 6	.96
Overall	.95

The whole scale internal consistency value of 0.95 poses an excellent score which is above the threshold value of 0.7. This means that there is an overall high level of reliability and consistency in the validation and evaluation of teachers and experts on the developed module. This means a high degree of agreement among the experts.

Evaluation of the Self-Learning Module by Teachers and Experts

Table 2. Overall Expert and Teacher Validation of the Self-Learning Module

		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
All	Objectives	4.82	0.29	4.68	0.47	4.75	0.38	Outstanding
	Content	4.72	0.36	4.69	0.47	4.71	0.42	Outstanding
	Organization	4.75	0.37	4.72	0.46	4.73	0.41	Outstanding
	Materials & Resources	4.80	0.29	4.75	0.43	4.77	0.36	Outstanding
	Effectiveness	4.85	0.22	4.73	0.44	4.79	0.33	Outstanding
	Overall	4.79	0.31	4.71	0.45	4.75	0.38	Outstanding

The table shows the overall results and scores of the evaluation of teachers and experts on the developed modules in teaching Araling Panlipunan 9 in terms of their objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectiveness.

The overall mean and standard deviation scores of the modules obtained were 4.75 and 0.38, respectively. These advantageous and satisfactory scores posit congruency and reliability from the scores obtained by each module. Further, the set criteria, which include the objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectiveness, deliberately tested and posted consistent and manageable results that signify that the modules' phases do not go against the following evaluation determiners and the competencies set forth by the curriculum.

This indicates that the modules utilized were well-designed and constructed based on the necessity assessed for meaningful and successful learning in the said course of study. The result affirms Jaramillo's (2002) statement that teachers should always strive hard to provide a learning environment and maintain the students' high interest. To achieve this, educators should use varied motivation and excellent teaching strategies and materials that include personally crafted modules that are subject to validation and evaluation.

In support of the satisfactory scores and results, the first expert evaluator provided a general comment on the six modules being validated:

"The modules were innovative and meaningful. These were designed following the objectives and competencies set by the curriculum in AP. At first glance, I thought that the first module was deliberately modified from a source, but the contents were adopted and properly cited. Activities were also interesting and very good."

A teacher from the South District further added and complimented the results, however, interestingly, the expert evaluator provided feedback on the criteria provided in the checklist:

"Honestly, I noticed upon checking the criteria on the checklist, that they go together. I reviewed the objectives in teaching the subject as I have been teaching it for several years in my former and current workplace; the objectives were met because the activities and assessment tools made a triangulation congruency. This means that the objectives were answered in the learning experiences and tests provided." For the materials, sources and authors were properly cited which is nice and accepted. I believe this is effective for students might be very interested and motivated by the activities and series of pictures inserted in the modules."

Finally, the teacher from the other school division in Isabela halted his comments and suggestions on the modules, he stated:

"Module 1 is good and interesting devised. As I checked and validated further the succeeding modules, I thought I was reading a book created by experts. I may use one of them and recommend it to other teachers I know who have been teaching the subject."

These descriptive comments and feedback from the evaluators further strengthen the initial claims from the validated and computed results. This means that the experts believed that the learning materials provided a topic course outline with relevant and significant learning activities and assessment tests. The self-learning module also provided sufficient information and features value-laden learning activities. Hence, the contents, activities, and assessment tools were appropriate considering their learning levels, needs, and learning capacities.

Remarkably, the present self-learning module meets the principles that Richards (2012) cited in Soriano (2013), emphasized. Those materials can be produced to meet

the student's needs that will reflect the local context, issues, and concerns. It can help develop expertise among professionals and provide a greater understanding of the characteristics of effective materials. On the other hand, the learning modules become inclusive to consider learners who are reluctant to attend classes or in cases of tardiness, the learning modules could be utilized to cope with the learning situation. The result also confirms Ramos' (2004) assertion that modules can also be used as a way to help students catch up on the missed lessons. The student will be able to work at his own pace while learning the missed topics, thus giving the student a chance to maximize learning. The use of modules could be seen as a better strategy to handle the situation as opposed to just letting the student copy the missed day's lectures from his/ her classmates without further understanding.

Table 3. Students' Evaluation of Format of the Self-Learning Module

Format	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The layout of the instructional modules is logically and sequentially arranged.	4.60	.49	Strongly Agree
2. The instructions in the modules are well-emphasized.	4.84	.37	Strongly Agree
3. The font size and font style of the instructional modules are readable.	4.80	.40	Strongly Agree
4. The mathematical symbols used in the instructional modules are well-defined.	4.75	.43	Strongly Agree
5. The tables/diagrams are well presented and easy to understand.	4.80	.40	Strongly Agree
6. Key points and key concepts are well highlighted to focus attention while reading.	4.82	.44	Strongly Agree
7. Titles and subtitles in the instructional modules are clearly defined.	4.71	.51	Strongly Agree
8. Illustrations, pictures, and captions are properly laid out for easy reference.	4.68	.51	Strongly Agree
9. The steps in the solutions of the given examples and practice tasks are arranged sequentially and easy to follow.	4.75	.43	Strongly Agree
10. The instructional modules are generally formatted in a convenient manner considering the paper size used.	4.73	.54	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.75	.15	Strongly Agree

The evaluation of students on the series of self-learning module provided to them as part of their learning experiences in the said subject. There was a consistent obtained score from the learners' evaluation of the learning modules. The overall mean rating of 4.75 and a standard deviation of 0.15 are described and interpreted as excellently devised and constructed learning modules. The technical aspects of

the learning modules that were evaluated include (a) the layout that is suited to the learning needs and levels of the learners; (b) logical and sequential orders of instructions, directions, contents, and other parts of the learning modules; (c) styles and sizes; (d) tables, diagrams, pictures, titles, and subtitles; and illustrative examples and paper conventions. Feedbacks from a students support the high rating in format.

“I like the module kasi maganda una pa lang pagtingin mo. Then, yung pictures and examples po na andun is very interesting po siya. My attention was to the pictures pona ginamit sa discussion ng mga concepts po and lessons. It is good and very pleasing to the eyes. I hope all my subjects have modules for us to study our lessons to learn.”

On a further note, the self-learning module met the criteria mentioned by Ramos (2004). The conventions in writing and devising learning modules as teaching aids must always be strictly considered and followed and there is a psychological effect of good and well-written learning modules in the perception of the students who use learning modules.

This may simply be added to the interest levels and motivation factors among learners in utilizing good modules. Nonetheless, there is no single identified learning module’s format and style. As Dahar (2011) opined, the best format for creating learning modules and other learning materials is dependent upon the needs, capacities, and levels of the learners who are to use the learning modules as identified by the teacher or the developer of the self-learning module.

Table 4. Students’ Evaluation of Content of the Self-Learning Module

Content	M	SD	Description
1. I easily understood the objectives of each lesson.	4.73	.49	SA
2. I easily understood the instructions in each lesson.	4.77	.42	SA
3. I could work on the lessons at my own pace.	4.91	.48	SA
4. I understood clearly the ideas/concepts in each lesson.	4.80	.40	SA
5. The illustrations guided me easily in following the instructions in the modules.	4.84	.37	SA
6. The learning activities helped me to understand the topic	4.68	.47	SA
7. I appreciated the styles of illustrations and written expressions.	4.71	.46	SA
8. I enjoyed answering the activity task as presented in the form of trivia or puzzles.	4.73	.49	SA
9. I found it easier to study Economics using these learning modules.	4.77	.42	SA
10. I enjoyed working through the lessons until I finished the whole learning module.	4.77	.42	SA
Overall	4.77	.13	SA

The students strongly agree on the evaluation of the content of the learning materials in the overall mean rating which is 4.77 and 0.13 for the standard deviation. The result reveals that the content competencies centered on the capacity and effectiveness of the self-learning module to aid the learning process on print materials is useful and appropriate. This demonstrates that the contents of the learning modules are very congruent to the learning objectives and competencies in the curriculum of the subject because the researcher strictly observed the principles on the impact and content aspect in writing instructional materials.

Table 5. Experts' and Students' Evaluation of Format of the Self-Learning Module

Format	Expert			Students		
	M	SD	Des	M	SD	Des.
1. The layout of the instructional modules is arranged in a logical and sequential order.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.59	0.50	SA
2. The instructions in the modules are well-emphasized.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.84	0.37	SA
3. The font size and font style of the instructional modules are readable.	4.33	0.58	A	4.80	0.41	SA
4. The mathematical symbols used in the instructional modules are well-defined.	4.00	1.00	A	4.75	0.44	SA
5. The tables/diagrams are well presented and easy to understand.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.80	0.41	SA
6. Key points and key concepts are well highlighted to focus attention while reading.	5.00	0.00	SA	4.82	0.45	SA
7. Titles and subtitles in the instructional modules are clearly defined.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.70	0.51	SA
8. Illustrations, pictures, and captions are properly laid out for easy reference.	4.33	0.58	A	4.68	0.52	SA
9. The steps in the solutions of the given examples and practice tasks are arranged sequentially and easy to follow.	4.00	0.00	A	4.75	0.44	SA
10. The instructional modules are generally formatted in a convenient manner considering the paper size used.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.73	0.54	SA
Overall	4.50	0.57	SA	4.75	0.46	SA

Based on the set of descriptions and criteria for the evaluation of the self-learning module's overall format, the module obtained a 'strongly agree' remark that brings favorable evaluation to the modules. Specifically, the modules' format had an overall

mean rating of 4.50 from the experts and 4.75 from the learners. Meanwhile, it also obtained a standard deviation of 0.57 and 0.46 from the experts and students, respectively. These data show that both the evaluators (experts and learners) strongly agree that the format, style, and overall face validity of the modules are satisfactory. These factors heighten the interest of anticipation upon reading and browsing the learning modules.

Table 6. Experts' and Students' Evaluation of Content of the Self-Learning Module

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. I easily understood the objectives of each lesson.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.73	0.50	SA
2. I easily understood the instructions in each lesson.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.77	0.42	SA
3. I could work on the lessons at my own pace.	4.00	1.00	A	4.91	0.29	SA
4. I understood clearly the ideas/concepts in each lesson.	4.33	0.58	A	4.80	0.41	SA
5. The illustrations/captions guided me easily in following the instructions in the modules.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.84	0.37	SA
6. The learning activities helped me to understand fully the topic.	5.00	0.00	SA	4.68	0.47	SA
7. I appreciated the styles of illustrations and written expressions.	4.33	0.58	A	4.70	0.46	SA
8. I enjoyed answering the activity task as presented in the form of trivia or puzzles.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.73	0.50	SA
9. I found it easier to study Economics using these learning modules.	5.00	0.00	SA	4.77	0.42	SA
10. I enjoyed working through the lessons until I finished the whole learning module.	4.67	0.58	SA	4.77	0.42	SA
Overall	4.60	0.56	SA	4.77	0.43	SA

On one hand, the preceding table further details the combined experts' and learners' evaluation of the content of the self-learning module. Based on the set of descriptions and criteria for the evaluation of the modules' overall content, the module obtained a 'strongly agree' remark that gives a favorable evaluation of the modules. Specifically, the modules' content had an overall mean rating of 4.60 from the experts and 4.77 from the learners. Meanwhile, it also obtained a standard deviation of 0.56 and 0.43 from the experts and students, respectively.

The data reveal a positive evaluation of the modular content by the learners and experts. As mentioned earlier, the content and other relevant inclusions in the modules were anchored from the competencies and objectives set forth by the Curriculum Guide of the Araling Panlipunan in the K – 12 Basic Education Curriculum. This is to ensure a relatively high congruence in learning expectations on the competencies and the experiences of the learners and the teaching expertise of the expert evaluators.

Table 7. Comparison Between Experts' and Students' Evaluation of the Format of the Self-Learning Module

Evaluators	<i>M</i>	<i>N</i> (items)	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i> (9)	<i>P</i>	<i>95CI</i>
Experts	4.60	10	.31	-	.16	[-.08, .42]
Students	4.77	10	.07	1.52 ^{ns}		

Evaluators	<i>M</i>	<i>N</i> (items)	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i> (9)	<i>P</i>	<i>95CI</i>
Experts	4.50	10	.33	-2.38*	.042	[.011, .48]
Students	4.74	10	.08			

It displays that despite the overall ratings of experts and students on the format of the self-learning module had the same descriptive rating of “strongly agree” (see Table 4), Paired samples t-test showed that the students ($M = 4.74$; $SD = .075$) indicated a significantly higher rating than the experts ($M = 4.50$; $SD = .33$), $t(9) = -2.38$, $p < .05$, $95CI$ from .011 to .48.

This significantly means that the learners - clientele of the study, responded positively on their utilization of the self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan. Consequently, this expressly implies that the format and style of the learning materials have a strong impact on learners' interest, satisfaction, and overall learning experience toward the subject.

Table 8. Comparison Between Experts' and Students' Evaluation of the Content of the Self-Learning Module

It shows that there was no significant difference between the ratings indicated by experts ($M = 4.60$; $SD = .31$) and students ($M = 4.77$; $SD = .07$) on the content of the module, $t(9) = -1.52$, $p > .16$. This means that the ratings obtained both correlatively agree on the evaluation of the content of the self-learning module.

The Effectiveness of the Self-learning Module in Teaching Araling Panlipunan 9

Table 9. Students' Performance in Araling Panlipunan 9 Before and After using the self-learningmodules

Material	Pretest		Posttest		t (44)	Sig(2-tailed)	Eta Squared
	M	SD	M	SD			
Module 1	2.37	1.64	8.66	1.66	-20.90***	.000	.91
Module 2	2.93	1.60	8.66	.90	-23.40***	.000	.92
Module 3	2.68	1.96	8.66	1.00	-22.89***	.000	.92
Module 4	2.91	1.80	9.11	1.02	-18.54***	.000	.89
Module 5	2.95	1.73	8.71	1.01	-19.62***	.000	.90
Module 6	3.00	1.75	8.62	1.55	-21.72***	.000	.91
Overall	13.57	4.54	34.77	4.31	-24.97***	.000	.93

Note. *** means significant at a .001 level

There was a significant difference between their pretest scores ($2.37 < M < 3.00$) and posttest scores ($8.62 < M < 9.11$) in all the modules, $-23.40 < t(44) < -18.54$, $p < .001$. Partial eta squared indicated that the effect size of the modules on the students' performance was large ranging from .89 to .93

Generally, there was a large significant difference between their overall pretest score ($M = 13.57$) and posttest score ($M = 34.77$), $t(44) = -24.97$, $p < .001$, *eta squared* = .93. Evidence suggests that the modules have enhanced the students' performance in the subject. The result accepts the finding of Agorilla (2015) that generally validated and evaluated learning materials have a significant impact on the learning development of students. Notably, the learning modules can be utilized as an intervention material since the materials meet one specific determinant on the innovation and design of learning modules as an intervention material.

The results of the pre-test and post-test are the best assessment tools to measure and evaluate the effectiveness of the innovative and designed learning material in teaching Araling Panlipunan 9 among Grade 10 students.

Jaramillo (2002), stated that the utilization of pre-test and post-test assessment

tools is an effective means to test significant changes after an identifiable learning intervention and should always be limited to the objectives of the learning modules or any learning materials necessary for the holistic development of learners. The statistical results and evaluation feedback from students and experts vouch for the validity and reliability of the contents, objectives, strategies, and assessment tools, as well as the design, format, and layout.

It can be deduced that the developed instructional modules in teaching Araling Panlipunan 10, specifically Economics, are relevant and effective in meeting the needs, interests, and abilities of students. The modules are ideal for classroom use as enrichment or intervention materials. Most importantly, the modules can lessen the problems with the availability of learning resources, appropriate learning materials, and the non-face-to-face modality.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the self-learning module developed for *Araling Panlipunan 9* is valid, reliable, and suitable for the learning levels, needs, and abilities of the students who use it. Teachers, experts, and students evaluated the modules with very high and consistent statistical results, showing unity in their ratings and positive feedback. The learning modules align with relevant guidelines and sources, meeting the study's objectives. These materials are effective in enriching students' knowledge, attitudes, and skills, and are easily comprehensible, allowing for ease of use by students. Additionally, incorporating the self-learning module alongside traditional teaching methods can effectively enhance the teaching of *Araling Panlipunan*, contributing to improved student achievement in the subject. The use of pre-tests and post-tests is the best way to assess the effectiveness of the developed learning materials in teaching *Araling Panlipunan 9*.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are given:

1. The developed and validated self-learning module in Araling Panlipunan 9 be used as developmental, enrichment, and intervention material in teaching Economics.
2. Interested future researchers may use the developed and validated modular format in preparing a complete set of self-learning modules for Araling Panlipunan 9 for the first, second, and third quarters.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Following ethical standards, this research adheres to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards all participants involved. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants, ensuring their understanding of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Confidentiality and

anonymity were preserved throughout data collection, analysis, and dissemination, safeguarding participants' privacy. Moreover, the researcher made sure that there was no conflict of interest in conducting the study, avoided plagiarism issues, and no bias was made in the interpretation of the results of the study. Finally, she ensured that the findings were used only for the research.

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